

Boiled Sweetpotato Food Target Product Profile Workplan, at CIP-Uganda & Peru

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Ethics: The activities, which led to the production of this document, were assessed and approved by the CIRAD Ethics Committee (H2020 ethics self-assessment procedure). When relevant, samples were prepared according to good hygiene and manufacturing practices. When external participants were involved in an activity, they were priorly informed about the objective of the activity and explained that their participation was entirely voluntary, that they could stop the interview at any point and that their responses would be anonymous and securely stored by the research team for research purposes.

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ABSTRACT

The RTBfoodomics project officially started with a kickoff and planning meeting organized at CIAT (Cali, Colombia) in March 2025. This gathering brought together the partners of the project to align on project activities and responsibilities. Defining a standard sampling protocol was of particular importance.

Following the meeting, CIP produced a detailed workplan outlining the genotypes to be harvested and the samples to be produced and analyzed. The sampling protocol was discussed at length to ensure enough replications of each genotype were included in the workplans (at planting, harvesting and sample preparation).

The phenotyping strategy at CIP-Uganda and Peru for boiled sweetpotato target some key sensory traits: aroma/flavour, firmness, and mealiness. Thirty-one genotypes, including elite breeding lines, landraces, and market varieties, were pre-selected based on descriptive sensory analysis (DSA) data collected between 2022 and 2024. Genotype selection prioritized aroma/flavour, followed by firmness and mealiness, with consideration of genotype × environment interactions across Namulonge and Rwebitaba. Phenotyping will be conducted using harmonized SOPs, including trained panel evaluations and instrumental texture profile analysis (TPA). Aroma and flavour will be assessed via metabolomic profiling of freeze-dried samples shipped to CIRAD (France).

Field trials will be planted in April 2025, with staggered harvesting beginning in September. From the initial 31 genotypes, 15 will be selected for detailed phenotyping and metabolomic analysis. Each genotype will be represented by six biological replicates, with samples prepared for sensory, texture, and metabolomic evaluation. Fast cooling and freeze-drying protocols will ensure sample integrity. Final sensory profiles will be triangulated with metabolomic data to explore correlations between chemical composition and human perception. This integrated approach supports the development of a robust food product profile for boiled sweetpotato, guiding breeding efforts toward consumer-preferred traits.

Key Words: Sweetpotato, Phenotyping, Descriptive Sensory Analysis (DSA), Texture Profile Analysis (TPA), Aroma, Flavour, Mealiness, Freeze-Drying, Metabolomic

1 PHENOTYPING SAMPLES

1.1 Phenotyping using harmonized SOPs: Core traits

The prioritized core traits for sweetpotato are aroma/flavour, firmness, and mealiness, listed in order of importance. These traits will be assessed by a **trained sensory panel** using previously validated and published procedures (<https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00601>). To ensure more representative sampling of the roots, however, each root portion will be sliced longitudinally rather than cross-sectionally.

In addition, firmness will be evaluated using instrumental methods, as detailed in a validated and published standard operating procedure (SOP) (<https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00749>). This SOP follows the texture profile analysis method, in which pieces of steamed sweetpotato of a standard size are compressed twice in succession using a plate probe.

1.2 Instrumental phenotyping for aroma and flavor

Sweetpotato samples will be prepared and **shipped to France for aroma and flavour screening**. Evidence suggests that representative volatile profiles can be obtained from freeze-dried sweetpotato samples. Pending agreement with the leader of the aroma/flavour component, freeze-dried samples may be used for this analysis.

2 DEFINITION OF GENOTYPES TO SCREEN.

2.1 Brief description of the origin of the genotypes to test

A group of genotypes within the breeding program (MDP and elite crosses) exhibiting a wide range of intensities for the core traits was pre-selected for the project. Selection was based on descriptive sensory analysis data collected between 2022 and 2024, during which trained panels evaluated samples for sweetpotato aroma and flavour, firmness in the mouth, and mealiness in the mouth. The genotypes were categorized according to established thresholds for these core traits (Nakitto et al., 2023). The cut-off average scores for each attribute and the corresponding trait categories are presented in **Table 1**. For genotypes evaluated more than once during this period, average scores were calculated and used for categorization. Since genotypes often fell into different categories across the traits, selection followed the established priority of core traits—i.e., genotypes were selected first based on sweetpotato aroma and flavour.

Table 1: Average scores for descriptive sensory attributes (DSA) and the cut-offs for each genotype category by core traits

Priority	Core trait	Sensory attribute	Poor	Intermediate Average score	Good
1	Aroma / flavour	Sweetpotato aroma	<4	4 - 5	≥6
		OR Sweetpotato flavour	<4	4 - 5	≥6
2	Firmness	Firmness in mouth	<3	3	≥4
3	Mealiness	Mealiness in mouth	<2	2 - 3	≥4

There is evidence of variation in sensory quality by location, indicating a strong genotype × environment interaction for these traits (Nakitto et al., 2023). As a result, selection was primarily based on data from the designated activity site, Namulonge, with consideration given to Rwebitaba as the backup site. Genotypes that were categorized similarly across both locations were prioritized for selection. Landraces that met the established criteria were also considered and included. Additionally, leading market varieties—**NAROSPOT 1** (white-fleshed) and **NASPOT 8** (orange-fleshed)—were incorporated into the selection.

2.2 List of genotypes

The list of 31 pre-selected genotypes and their categories based on core traits is shown in **Table 2**. The material will tentatively be planted in Namulonge in April 2025, with harvesting expected to begin in September 2025, which corresponds to the usual first season of the year.

The distribution of average sweetpotato aroma, sweetpotato flavour, firmness in the mouth, and mealiness in the mouth is illustrated in **Figure 1**. For this set of pre-selected genotypes, sweetpotato aroma ranged from **3 to 8**, sweetpotato flavour ranged from **1 to 8**, firmness in the mouth ranged from **1 to 6**, and mealiness in the mouth (crumbliness) ranged from **0 to 9**.

Correlations among the descriptive sensory analysis (DSA) average scores for the four attributes were analysed using the Spearman Rank Correlation test. The results (**Table 3**) revealed a strong positive relationship between sweetpotato aroma and flavour, as well as between firmness in the mouth and crumbliness in the mouth. A moderate correlation was observed between sweetpotato aroma and crumbliness in the mouth, while no significant correlation was found between sweetpotato flavour and either of the texture attributes.

2.3 Alternative back-up germplasm or sources of sampling

Namulonge is located in the hotspot zone for SPVD. To mitigate the risk of loss of this material, back-up germplasm will be planted in Rwebitaba. However, if this (back-up) material is used, the number of replicates may have to be reduced since staggered harvesting could be challenging.

Three weeks before the planting date, vines of **30 pre-selected sweetpotato genotypes** will be obtained from the greenhouse and **multiplied under swampy conditions** to produce adequate amount of good-quality planting material. The sweetpotato vines will then be planted on-station in **Namulonge** during the **April rainy season**, with **seven plots per genotype and 30 plants per plot**. In Namulonge, sweetpotato typically reaches maturity in four months.

Table 2: Summary of the 31 genotypes pre-selected to screen.

Genotype	Phenotype category		
	Aroma and flavour ¹	Firmness ²	Mealiness ³
MUWULU-ADUDUMA	Good	Good	Good
NAROSPOT 1	Good	Good	Good
SILK OMUYAKA	Good	Good	Good
TANZANIA	Good	Good	Good
UGP2017 0341-20	Good	Good	Good
UGP2020 00296-13	Good	Good	Good
UGP2020 00296-41	Good	Good	Good
UGP2020 00062-16	Good	Good	Intermediate
CIP1990 62-1	Good	Good	Poor
UGP2020 00052-10	Good	Good	Poor
UGP2020 00302-5	Good	Good	Poor
UGP2020 00276-5	Intermediate	Good	Good

UGP2020 00296-42	Intermediate	Good	Good
UGP2020 00302-12	Intermediate	Good	Good
UGP2020 00283-20	Intermediate	Good	Intermediate
UGP2020 00052-16	Intermediate	Good	Intermediate
UGP2020 00004-19	Intermediate	Good	Intermediate
UGP2020 00283-40	Intermediate	Intermediate	Intermediate
UGP2020 00283-40	Intermediate	Intermediate	Intermediate
UGP2020 00241-9	Intermediate	Good	Poor
UGP2020 00268-5	Intermediate	Good	Poor
UGP2020 00070-14	Intermediate	Intermediate	Poor
UGP2017 0024-11	Intermediate	Poor	Poor
UGP2017 0274-4	Poor	Good	Good
UGP2017 0481-3	Poor	Good	Good
UGP2017 0902-54	Poor	Good	Good
UGP2020 00301-7	Poor	Good	Good
UGP2020 00283-26	Poor	Good	Good
UGP2017 0490-966	Poor	Intermediate	Poor
BEAUREGARD	Poor	Poor	Poor
UGP2014 0117-14	Poor	Poor	Poor

¹ “poor” - sweetpotato aroma or sweetpotato flavor < 4; “intermediate” - sweetpotato aroma or flavour = 4 -5; “good” – sweetpotato aroma or flavour ≥6

² “poor” – firmness in mouth <3; “intermediate” – firmness in mouth =3; “good” – firmness in mouth =3

³ “poor” – mealiness in mouth <2; “intermediate” – mealiness in mouth = 2 – 3; “good” – mealiness in mouth ≥4

Table 3: Spearman ranks correlation among average scores for sweetpotato aroma, sweetpotato flavour, firmness in mouth and crumbliness in mouth scores as rated by trained sensory panel for the pre-selected genotypes (n=31).

	Sweetpotato aroma	Sweetpotato flavor	Firmness	Crumbliness
Sweetpotato aroma	1.000			
Sweetpotato flavor	0.603	1.000		
Firmness/ Hardness	0.242	-0.099	1.000	
Crumbliness	0.502	0.138	0.741	1.000

Figure 1: Histograms showing distribution of average scores for sweetpotato aroma (Top left), sweetpotato flavour (Top right), firmness in mouth (bottom left) and mealiness in mouth or crumbliness (bottom right) of 31 pre-selected genotypes as rated by a trained

3 SAMPLING STRATEGY AND EXPERIMENTAL DESIGN

3.1 Environmental/physiological conditions during the phenotyping process

An extra (screening plot) with 30 plants for each genotype will be harvested one week before ideal maturity and used to screen for the most suitable genotypes that represent a broad range of core traits (aroma/flavour, firmness, and mealiness). The data generated will be used to select the final set of 15 genotypes for phenotyping and metabolomic analysis (Figure 2). The remaining six plots of each selected genotype will then be harvested at ideal maturity, plot by plot, over a three-week period. These harvests will be used for sensory phenotyping by a trained panel and for instrumental texture analysis, as described in Section 1.1. Samples from these harvests will also be collected, processed (via freezing or freeze-drying), and shipped for metabolomic analysis and instrumental assessment of aroma and flavour.

3.2 Field genotype selection

A final set of 15 genotypes that best represent ‘poor’, ‘intermediate’, and ‘good’ quality sweetpotato—based on the three core traits: aroma/flavour, firmness, and mealiness—will be selected from the 31 pre-identified genotypes listed in Table 2.

To determine this final set, a trained sensory panel (<https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00573>, <https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00582>) will evaluate samples (n = 31) using an abridged version of the sensory lexicon, focusing on proxy attributes related to key traits: sweetpotato aroma, sweetpotato flavour, firmness in the mouth, and mealiness in the mouth. Panelists will undergo rigorous training in advance to

mitigate the risk of attribute dumping. As outlined in **Section 2.1** and **Table 1**, defined thresholds for these attributes will be used to categorize the genotypes and refine the selection to the final set of 15.

Figure 2: Illustration of the general strategy for planting, harvesting, phenotyping and sampling processes of the metabolomic study of boiled sweetpotato (for details see Figures 3 and 4)

3.3 Biological replicates

For this project, a **biological replicate** refers to roots collected from a plot consisting of 30 plants. All seven plots will be established in the same field and planted simultaneously. Harvesting, however, will be staggered, with the first plot of **all genotypes** ($n = 15$) being harvested, phenotyped, and sampled first (**Figure 2**). This will be followed by harvesting, phenotyping, and sample preparation for the second set of plots for all genotypes, and so on through the six plots available. All harvesting and phenotyping activities are expected to be completed within three weeks from the first harvest date.

3.4 Field sampling

From each replicate of the final set of 15 genotypes, **fifteen damage-free storage roots of moderate size** will be randomly selected per genotype at harvest (**Figures 2 and 3**). The root samples will be placed in woven sample bags to ensure good airflow and transported to the laboratories within 24 hours. Five roots will be randomly selected and used for **texture analysis in Namulonge** using established procedures. The remaining ten roots will be used for evaluation by a **trained sensory panel in Kawanda**, and for the preparation and shipment of samples to RHUL (UK) for **metabolomic analysis** and to CIRAD (France) for **instrumental assessment of flavor and aroma**.

3.5 Sampling for metabolomic analysis

Before cooking the ten roots for descriptive sensory analysis, a portion of 7 cm length central portion will be cut out from the root and **longitudinally halved**. A **thin longitudinal slice** will be collected **from each half** and placed in separate labelled plastic bags. One bag will be assigned to RHUL and the other to CIRAD (**Figure 4**). Longitudinal slice is preferred over a cross-sectional cut as it is expected to be more representative of the variation along the root.

After collecting the raw slices, the remaining portions of the root (from which the raw sample is collected) will then be cooked following SOP. Another set of thin **longitudinally cut slices** will be collected **from the cooked halves** and similarly placed in separate labelled bags. **Each slice will be packed separately** to allow for representative sampling when homogenizing samples in the RHUL and CIRAD labs. It is expected that 10 slices for each replicate shall supply more than 1g required by RHUL and 10g required by CIRAD.

Figure 3: Flow diagram showing schematic workflow summarising sampling; DSA = descriptive sensory analysis with trained panel; TPA = texture profile analysis using instrumental texture analyser.

Figure 4: Illustration of the procedure followed for the preparation of cooked samples.

A 7cm section from each of ten roots is taken from the central portion of the root. The section is then longitudinally split into two halves. A longitudinal slice is taken from one of the halves (Half-A in the diagram), which is used as raw sample of the root. The other half (Half-B in the diagram) and the rest of Half-A are then cooked together. A longitudinal slice is taken from the cooked Half-B, which is used as cooked sample of the root. The remains of the cooked samples are pooled together and used for sensory evaluation by a trained panel. The raw and cooked slices are shipped to RHUL (freeze-dried) and CIRAD (frozen or freeze-dried).

Fast cooling samples: After collecting all 10 slices for each treatment, the sample bags will be quickly flushed with liquid nitrogen, where possible. The bags will be placed in a cooler box with liquid nitrogen and transported from Kawanda to Namulonge. In Namulonge they will be freeze-dried. However, pending on ongoing research, samples to be shipped to CIRAD may be frozen or freeze-dried.

Packaging and Shipment: Each slice will be kept in its separate primary packaging to facilitate more representative homogenization and sampling at the lab level. The packaging will be labelled well to include information about the genotype, root number and treatment (raw or cooked). Freeze-dried (but not milled) samples will be shipped via a trusted courier (DHL) to the respective labs.

Quality control: **Blinded replicates** will be included in the sample batches shipped to the laboratories for metabolomic analysis.

3.6 Sensory evaluation of collected samples

All the 6 replicates of the 15 genotypes shipped to RHUL and CIRAD laboratories will be evaluated by a trained sensory panel. The sensory profiles for each replicate will be triangulated with metabolomic data to determine the relationship between human sensory perceptions and metabolomic composition. To do this, the portion of the cooked root that remains after collecting the lab samples (**Figure 4**) will be evaluated by a trained panel following routine practice. Previous work shows that flavour could be influenced by other sensory attributes, especially texture (Allan et al., 2024) and thus for **the final 15 genotypes** the aim will be to obtain a **complete sensory profile**.

4 CHRONOGRAM OF ACTIVITIES

A chronogram showing timelines for the planned completed, ongoing and planned activities including planting, harvesting, processing and sample shipment is presented in **Figure 5**.

Figure 5: Tentative chronogram of project activities for sweetpotato RTBfoodomics in Uganda

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